

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Version: 1.0.0

The NFDI Template Framework

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About this document

DMP4NFDI is the basic service in development for data management planning within the NFDI. The basic service is realized within the Base4NFDI framework and currently in the second of three development stages, the integration phase. The main objective is to support NFDI consortia in the improvement and provision of standardized data and software management plan services. DMP4NFDI hosts the DMP platform RDMO for consortia, defines templates / structures, supports integration of RDMO with NFDI or other consortia services, offers training and outreach support.

This document describes the NFDI DMP Template Framework (TF) and illustrates its use. The framework is intended to serve as a uniform standard for DMP template development for the NFDI consortia and to provide an initial basic DMP template (NFDI DMP Template). At the same time, it is openly available, and suitable for reuse.

The text contains terms that have a specific meaning in RDMO. These are explained in advance under [X.II](#).

The [first chapter](#) discusses the history of the basic service and the vision behind the framework.

The [second chapter](#) presents and analyzes the entire development of the TF based on mappings to the RDA maDMP (Miksa et al., Version 1.1), showing which areas have been adopted in what way.

Furthermore, there are two perspectives on the TF described in this document:

1. It is a way to harmonize content, based on the schema for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (RDA maDMP) published by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) DMP Common Standards Working Group. The mappings are presented and explained in detail in [Chapter 3](#).
2. It is a structured DMP which uses the mapped attributes, and can be reused as an RDMO catalog. [Chapter 4](#) explains the areas in more detail and illustrates their reuse.

The catalog is in its first version and focuses on DMPs. SMPs will be integrated into this model in the future. Starting in the integration phase, it will be supplemented and refined with the help of NFDI consortia. Further ideas for the next version of the TF already exist and are explained in more detail in [Chapter 5](#).

Finally, we express our thanks to all those involved who have contributed in various ways to the TF in its current form – whether through discussions and feedback during workshops and lectures, or further development through text suggestions, ideas, and explanations in separate meetings.

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X. Abbreviations and Definitions

X.I Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP4NFDI	Basic Service “Data Management Plans for the NFDI”
maDMP	machine-actionable Data Management Plan
NFDI	(German) National Research Data Infrastructure
NFDI DMP Template	The NFDI DMP Template Framework as a questionnaire in RDMO
	RDA Research Data Alliance
RDA maDMP	RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans by the RDA workgroup "DMP Common Standards" ¹
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMO	Research Data Management Organiser
SMP	Software Management Plan
TF	NFDI DMP Template Framework
WG LTA	Working group ‘Long Term Access and Preservation’ of the NFDI section ‘Common Infrastructures’

X.II Definition of Terms

Since the work on the TF is based on RDMO, the following terms should be explained. Additional explanations are available in the official RDMO documentation².

Attributes are the RDMO-internal variables which are used to store the information contained in a DMP in a structured way as key-value pairs. Values will be assigned when a user fills in a questionnaire (*catalog*). The attribute values are then available for further processing, export, validation, and transfer to other RDM services.

A **Catalog** in RDMO is a set of questions defining an interview in RDMO. It is organized hierarchically into sections, pages, *question sets*, and *questions*.

A **Collection** in RDMO allows the user to answer the same *questions* for different kinds of sets. This is often used to create several *datasets*.

¹ While the official name is called “standard” (Miksa et al., Version 1.1), we will use the term **schema** when we mention it.

² <https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/management/catalog-development.html#basics>

A **Dataset** is a specific *collection* available in many RDMO *catalogs*. It is used to allow the user to answer the same *questions* for different types of methods or data types within the research project.

The **Domain** represents the sum of all *attributes* in an RDMO instance. While the folder in the official RDMO GitHub repository is still called *domain*³, the section in RDMO has been renamed to *attributes*. This section can be accessed via the management interface. In this document “domain” refers to the list of attributes defined and shipped by the RDMO software.

An **Interview** refers to the act of responding to a *catalog* in RDMO, which can be accessed via the “answer questions” button.

Questions in an RDMO *catalog* can be asked at the project level and at the collection level, e.g. for each *dataset*. When designing a catalog, it should be kept in mind that it can be very tedious for a user to have to answer too many questions at the dataset level. It is therefore important to consider which questions relate to the total amount of data or to the higher-level (project) scope, and which questions should be answered in such detail that they are asked at the dataset level.

Question sets are a related group of *questions* that appear on one page, and for which it is possible to specify additional settings.

A **Template** is a structured model for creating a DMP, usually defined by sections and *questions*. The framework provides guidelines for the structure of a template to ensure compatibility. The implementation of a template in RDMO is called *catalog*. The **NFDI DMP Template Framework** refers to the mapping, the structure of the theoretical model, the standardized use of attributes, and rules and recommendations for creating framework-compatible content. The **NFDI DMP Template** refers to the implementation of the NFDI DMP Template Framework as a catalog in RDMO.

³ <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/main/rdmorganiser/domain>

1. Background

Since 2021 a working group in the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) on Data Management Plans (DMPs) has been consolidating DMP developments across the NFDI consortia. Later on, this working group was integrated within the NFDI Section ‘Common Infrastructures’ as *infra-dmp*. In its charta, *infra-dmp* defined several key objectives and measures to be taken to foster collaboration between the consortia (Enke et al., 2023). Based on several workshops, a vision paper was developed, which describes the goal of connected and machine-actionable DMPs across consortia and services (Diederichs et al., 2024). The working group identified necessary prerequisites in order to establish this vision, i.e. an agreement on a common vocabulary and a standardized framework for DMPs that can be utilized by all consortia. Based on this agreement, it is possible for the consortia to cooperatively develop services and templates for DMPs as well as plugins for connecting additional services.

The cross-consortia service DMP4NFDI started working on this standardization effort in June 2024 and created the *NFDI DMP Template Framework (TF)*, based on the schema for machine-actionable DMPs (Miksa et al., 2020) developed by a working group of the international Research Data Alliance (RDA). This framework supports consortia in the development of interoperable DMP templates by defining a common vocabulary, a structure and set of topics for DMPs, and value ranges for elements necessary to establish interoperability.

The framework is developed with the focus of implementation in the Research Data Management Organiser (Klar et al., RDMO), a DMP software tool broadly used by universities and non-university research institutions across Germany. The NFDI RDMO clients are hosted by DMP4NFDI. The framework in its essence does not require a specific tool, but builds on the internal vocabulary of RDMO (“attributes”) which allows a mapping between different templates. The framework maps the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (RDA maDMP) with the Science Europe Core Requirements for DMPs (Science Europe, 2021) – used e.g. in the DFG checklist⁴ – and questions frequently used in RDMO.

The framework was developed in several workshops and feedback loops with NFDI consortia and the national research data management community, and its first version is presented in this paper. This will allow consortia to start developing DMP templates based on this framework or map existing templates. Further refinements and integrations like software management plans (SMPs) are planned for upcoming versions (Castro et al., 2023).

⁴ http://www.dfg.de/research_data/checklist

2. Method

In order to exchange information between digital systems, all systems involved must have common agreements: what information they want to exchange, the form in which the information must be available, and how it is uniquely named. To make a DMP machine-readable, the values (“answers”) must therefore be made identifiable in some form according to these criteria. In RDMO, this is done using the attributes (see [X.II](#)) assigned to each question. Until now, however, there have been no strict guidelines on which attributes should be assigned to which questions. The aim of DMP4NFDI is therefore to define the attributes in such a way that each attribute can be assigned to a unique content. Therefore, the NFDI DMP Template Framework (TF) was built upon the RDA maDMP developed by the RDA (Miksa et al., 2020), which attempts to comprise all important areas in a DMP. The RDA maDMP is an internationally developed schema with clear and specific explanations.

In the course of this chapter, [Step 1](#) describes the process of determining which attribute in RDMO represents the corresponding RDA maDMP specification and is therefore selected for the TF. This mapping step is important for connecting RDMO to other systems via plugins, as the attributes must be digitally addressable in order to obtain the desired information. It also lays the foundation for the development of further interoperable RDMO catalogs, because if the respective attributes are used as specified in the TF, a plugin can also be used in several catalogs.

In addition to this mapping, the TF was also implemented as a catalog that can be reused in RDMO – the **NFDI DMP Template**. This catalog contains all attributes that are mapped to the RDA maDMP as in Step 1. However, further content analysis was required to develop the catalog. Other catalogs were primarily used as a basis for the outline and content structure. This is described in [Step 2](#).

Individual subject areas were then further expanded in terms of content. Various meetings with different working groups were held for this purpose, as described in [Step 3](#).

[Step 4](#) analyzes the extent to which the quality criteria formulated as the catalog's objectives by the infra-dmp working group (Enke et al., 2023) could be implemented.

Step 1: Mapping the RDMO attributes to the RDA maDMP properties

The RDA maDMP schema (Miksa et al., Version 1.1) organizes information in a hierarchical way. On the top level are the overarching subjects, such as "DMP", "project", "dataset", whose relationships (including the DMP4NFDI extensions) are shown in Figure 1.

For the TF the RDA maDMP was extended to include project contact information as well as additional legal questions ('Legal issues') that are part of the DFG checklist⁵, but cannot be represented in the RDA maDMP so far.

Figure 1 High-level structure of the NFDI DMP Template Framework: blue = information blocks inherited from the RDA maDMP, black = information blocks added by our workgroup.

Each topic in the RDA maDMP is further specified by lower-level fields – the properties – which can point to single pieces of information or to nested data structures that are composed of more fields. An example is shown in Figure 2:

Name	Description	Data Type	Cardinality	Example Value
funder_id	Identifier of a funder	Nested Data Structure	1	
funding_status	To express different phases of project lifecycle. Allowed Values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> planned applied granted rejected 	Term from Controlled Vocabulary	0..1	granted
grant_id	Identifier of a grant	Nested Data Structure	0..1	1234567

Figure 2 Example of documentation of properties from the RDA maDMP repository (Miksa et al., Version 1.1). Here: information on funding

⁵ <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/174736/92691e48e89bf4ac88c8eb91b8f783b0/forschungsdaten-checkliste-en-data.pdf>

- The name specifies the unique identifier of the property, which is also referenced when information is exchanged between different systems.
- The description specifies which information is stored in the property.
- The data type defines the data format and input type of the property values, to allow data validation and ensure interoperability between different systems. At the moment, these types are allowed: Boolean; Date; DateTime; Nested Data Structure; Number; String; Term from Controlled Vocabulary; URL.⁶
- The cardinality indicates how many times a property can be used (e.g. 1 = unique).
- In addition, an example value is given.

When catalogs are created in RDMO, each question is assigned an attribute that indicates the expected content input by a user and mediates this content between the various objects in RDMO. To develop the TF, the attributes available in the RDMO domain⁷ (see [X.II](#)) were mapped to the appropriate RDA maDMP properties. Therefore, questions assigned to the attributes across various catalogs were examined (see [step 2](#)).

RDMO also stores information in a hierarchical tree. Each attribute is identifiable by an URI, e.g.

- <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/costs/creation/personnel>
 - consisting of a **prefix** (<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms>)
 - and an assigned **path** (project/costs/creation/personnel), which reports its position in the hierarchy.
 - For each type of object in RDMO, an additional component is added, e.g. “domain”. In this case it is used to indicate that it is an attribute.

The attribute reported above refers to a question about personnel costs incurred in a project concerning data creation. An attribute can only occur once in each catalog and should reflect the scope of the assigned question as precisely as possible. By using the same attribute in the same context in different catalogs or platforms, information can be exchanged between them. For that purpose, (1) it is important to define the scope of an attribute as specifically as possible, without restricting it too much, and (2) attributes should primarily be selected from the list of attributes maintained by the RDMO community to ensure interoperability between catalogs. Additional attributes may be added to the domain with care, to avoid duplication or overlap.

At the same time, the correct use and identification of a suitable attribute is currently challenging, as an explicit definition is often missing and the scope can only be assessed by examining DMP questions referencing it. The NFDI DMP Template Framework aims to avoid such uncertainties by specifying usage and scope of each attribute in relation to selected, relevant DMP templates, similarly to the RDA maDMP (see [Chapter 3](#)).

⁶ <https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/management/catalog-development.html#widget-type>

⁷ <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/domain/attributes.xml>

Step 2: Analysis of existing DMP catalogs

The next step was to examine the questions assigned to the attributes in various catalogs. The RDMO core catalog⁸, the Horizon Europe template⁹, and the DFG checklist¹⁰ served as the most important references for this.

The **RDMO core catalog** contains 125 questions and is the most comprehensive of the three. It was developed by the RDMO community and therefore uses the attributes in the manner originally intended.

The **Horizon Europe catalog** is also quite comprehensive, with 84 questions. Its development was based on version 1.0 of the provided data management plan template¹¹.

The **DFG checklist catalog** implements the checklist provided by the DFG¹² as an RDMO catalog. This catalog was selected because it covers the *Core Requirements for Data Management Plans*¹³ defined by Science Europe, and has already been used as the basis for subject-specific templates by two NFDI consortia.

- NFDI4Chem has gathered information from their community by conducting several workshops, interviews, and surveys in order to enrich the template with chemistry-specific help texts and answer options and made it available as an RDMO catalog¹⁴ and as a PDF file (Hausen & Andres, 2024).
- NFDI4ING also gathered information in a survey and through community workshops to develop the template. The template has already been evaluated in further workshops, for example at the *FDM4Ing Community Meeting CC-42* (Hastik et al., 2023) with different user groups. As a result, a modified second version is already available.¹⁵

To ensure that attributes continue to be used consistently in the future, it was necessary to ensure that the appropriate attributes were mapped to the respective properties for the template framework. This is the key aspect when it comes to standardizing templates in RDMO.

Figure 3 illustrates the steps to find the right attribute. These steps can be shortened depending on the experience of a user with the RDMO vocabulary.

⁸ <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-rdmo.xml>

⁹ <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-horizon-europe.xml>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-DFG-Checkliste.xml>

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/template-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

¹² <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/174736/92691e48e89bf4ac88c8eb91b8f783b0/forschungsdaten-checkliste-en-data.pdf>

¹³ <https://scienceeurope.org/media/urspcz0a/se-rdm-template-1-core-requirements-for-data-management-plans.docx>

¹⁴ https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/shared/nfdi4chem/NFDI4Chem_FULL_RDMO2.xml

¹⁵ https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/shared/nfdi4ing/NFDI4Ing_Vorlage.xml

Figure 3 Steps to find the right attribute for a property

1. The lists of properties provided by the RDA have to be evaluated in terms of content in order to link the type of information requested in the RDMO catalogs.
2. The questions in the reference catalogs can be used to identify the desired output to be provided by users.
3. If this matches the content of the respective property, the attribute used for the questions can be mapped.
 - a. For this purpose, a Python script was created that extracts which attributes were used in the respective catalogs along with their question types.

All mappings of attributes to properties are described and explained in detail in Chapter 3. While the questions in the TF were based on this mapping, the sections and pages were organized according to the overarching themes and adapted in a slightly modified form to the core requirements of Science Europe¹⁶.

The color coding of the individual sections is intended solely to facilitate comparison of the content structure with the reference catalogs and is based on the section topics: Yellow = general project information; red = data description and so on.

¹⁶ <https://scienceeurope.org/media/urspcz0a/se-rdm-template-1-core-requirements-for-data-management-plans.docx>

a. The DFG Checklist Template in RDMO

Figure 4 shows the original division of sections and pages in the DFG checklist Template. The different colors indicate that similar questions have been transferred to the NFDI DMP Template. This is also intended to illustrate the extent to which the structure of the NFDI DMP Template is based on the structure of this template.

Section: Data Description	Section: Documentation and Data Quality	Section: Storage and technical protection measures during the project	Section: Legal obligations and conditions	Section: Data exchange and long-term data accessibility	Section: Responsibilities and resources
Page: Contentwise data description	Page: Documentation	Page: Data storage during the project	Page: Publication restrictions	Page: Reuse	Page: Responsibilities
Page: Technical Data Description	Page: Data Quality	Page: Technical data archiving during the project	Page: Scientific specifics	Page: Archival	Page: Resources
			Page: Legal Restrictions		

Figure 4 Content division in the DFG Checklist

- The chapters of the DFG catalog are organized according to the DFG checklist and Science Europe's guidelines for mandatory topics in a DMP.
- Due to the general and basic character of the DFG checklist, most of the questions could be easily mapped to the RDA maDMP properties. Thus, we used the checklist catalog as the foundation for the TF.
- The questions on *Scientific Specifics* and *Legal Restrictions* pages could not be assigned to any properties. In order to still fully include the DFG checklist into the TF, and to capture the Science Europe Core Requirements (Science Europe, 2021), these were included in a new node below the entity *DMP* and added to the template in RDMO as first and last sections.
- The TF structure is mainly based on this catalog with minimal changes. The TF begins with a general section on the project and responsibilities, which are spread over two sections in the DFG checklist. The sections *Legal obligations and conditions* and *Data exchange and long-term data accessibility* were swapped due to a logical order of the questions.

b. The Horizon Europe Template in RDMO

Figure 5 shows the division of sections and pages in the Horizon Europe Template.

Section: General	Section: Disciplinary and technical classification of data	Section: FAIR data	Section: Other research outputs	Section: Allocation of resources	Section: Data security	Section: Ethics	Section: Other aspects
Page: Basic information on the project	Page: Created or re-used	Page: Findability	Page: Other research outputs	Page: Costs	Page: Security measures	Page: Personal data	Page: Rules of the funders
	Page: Data type	Page: Accessibility: repository		Page: Responsibility		Page: Other sensitive data	Page: Project partners
	Page: Purpose	Page: Accessibility: data		Page: Preservation		Page: Official approval	Page: Other RDM regulations
	Page: Data volume	Page: Accessibility: data access committee		Page: Selection		Page: Intellectual property rights I	
	Page: Provenance	Page: Accessibility: metadata				Page: Intellectual property rights II	
	Page: Data utility	Page: Accessibility: Interoperability					
		Page: Re-usability					

Figure 5 Content division in the Horizon Europe catalog

- Although the questions in the catalog are divided into eight sections, the color coding shows that individual topics identified in the DFG checklist are dealt with across multiple sections. For example, questions about costs and responsibilities are not asked in a single section, but are divided among the different contents.
- The catalog is quite extensive with 84 questions that sometimes overlap in content.
- The division of chapters or pages based on the individual FAIR acronyms, as in the Horizon Europe catalog, is therefore a good starting point to explain these acronyms to the researchers. Instead of dividing the chapters and pages based on acronyms, the next version of the TF will have a stronger focus on explaining them.

c. The RDMO core Template

Section: General	Section: Content classification	Section: Technical classification	Section: Data usage	Section: Metadata and referencing	Section: Legal and ethics	Section: Storage and long-term preservation
Page: Topic	Page: Data sets	Page: Data collection	Page:	Page: Metadata	Page: General legal issues	Page: Selection
Page: Research field	Page: Data origin	Page: Data size	Usage scenarios	Page: Metadata costs	Page: Personal data	Page: Long-term preservation
Page: Project schedule	Page: Reuse	Page: Formats	Page: Data organisation	Page: Structure, granularity, and referencing	Page: Data protection	Page: Long-term preservation costs
Page: Project coordination	Page: Reproducibility	Page:	Page: Data storage and security	Page: Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)	Page: Sensitive data	
Page: Project partners		Tools	Page: Interoperability	Page: PID costs	Page: Other sensitive data	
Page: Funding		Page: Versioning	Page:		Page: Sensitive data costs	
Page: Other requirements			Data sharing and reuse		Page: Official approval	
			Page: Collaborative work		Page: Intellectual property rights I	
			Page: Quality assurance		Page: Intellectual property rights II	
			Page: Data integration		Page: Intellectual property rights costs	
			Page: Costs			

Figure 6 Content division in the RDMO core catalog

- With 7 sections and 43 pages, this catalog is very comprehensive and relies on extensive knowledge of a user, making it unsuitable as an introductory basic catalog. However, as it covers 125 questions, all topics are examined in great detail. The RDMO catalog asks, for example, whether the datasets can be divided into even smaller blocks and whether some parts can be published while other data of the

dataset cannot, whether there are different versioning strategies for parts of the datasets, and so on.

- To remain close to the RDA maDMP, we chose not to integrate many of these detailed questions. In future iterations, specific modules will be created that might reuse parts.

In exchange with the basic service PID4NFDI¹⁷, we are currently discussing how individual datasets can be made inter-referenceable; in order to examine to what extent a machine-readable implementation can cover the smaller division of the datasets and their versioning.

d. The NFDI DMP Template

Section: General Information	Section: Data Description	Section: Documentation and Data Quality	Section: Storage during the Project	Section: Data Exchange and long-term Data Accessibility	Section: Legal obligations and conditions
Page: General Project Information	Page: Content Data Description	Page: Data Documentation	Page: Data Storage	Page: Reuse	Page: Publication Restrictions
Page: Project Funding	Page: Technical Data Description	Page: Data Quality	Page: Backup	Page: Sharing	
Page: General DMP Information				Page: Archiving and Digital Preservation	
Page: Legal Restrictions regarding the Research Project and DMP					
Page: Responsibilities and Resources					

Figure 7 Content division in the NFDI DMP Template

- The first section of the NFDI DMP template deals with general project issues and overarching topics relating to costs and contact persons. It also contains information on the *data management responsibilities and resources* required by Science Europe.

All in all, we tried to make the TF as compact and comprehensive as possible. To ensure this, we have engaged in intensive discussions with several focus groups.

¹⁷ <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>

Step 3: Shaping individual topic areas with focus groups

For the new node on *Legal Issues*, we reviewed the relevance, completeness, and comprehensibility of the questions and help texts in the existing RDMO catalogs. Base4NFDI supported us with expertise, offering guidance not only on questions specifically related to data protection but also reviewing all inquiries relevant to the data lifecycle where legal considerations need to be addressed before passing them on to the task force. This ensured that the questions were comprehensive and free of any content gaps.

The reference catalogs also contained gaps and vaguely defined questions regarding long-term archiving (LTA). The NFDI working group Long Term Access and Preservation (WG LTA) of the section ‘Common Infrastructures’ (Markus et al., 2025) supported us in refining the relevant questions. Significant adjustments have been made to the help texts, and introductory explanations of terms are now available. The most significant change is the consequent use of the term *digital preservation*¹⁸, which conforms to the current EOSC strategy.

The question of automated transfer of information to other systems, as envisaged for the TF as a maDMP, also makes it necessary to consider referencing through PIDs. For this reason, we have engaged in discussions with the PID4NFDI basic service which resulted in a large number of possible connection points. PIDs could be used to reference datasets (e.g. DOI), persons (e.g. ORCID), organizations (e.g. ROR), instruments (ePIC, DOI), or for the DMP itself (DMP ID).

Figure 8 PID metadata and research object information flow¹⁹

Figure 8 shows how data flows through the different stages within the research data life cycle and highlights potential use to PIDs within DMPs. The list is not exhaustive, but can be used as a starting point. In addition, when thinking about how individual datasets can be

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

¹⁹ This visualization was created by [Sara El-Gebali](#) and can be reused under CC BY-SA 4.0

made inter-referenceable, we are also exploring whether it should be possible to assign unique references to collection set items within RDMO.

Step 4: Quality criteria achieved in the Template Framework

As we analyzed various catalogs to develop the TF, the *infra-dmp* working group (Enke et al., 2023), as part of the NFDI section ‘Common Infrastructures’²⁰, analyzed various catalogs to develop quality criteria for DMP templates (Krause et al., 2024). The criteria were divided into five categories, each of which requires different levels of effort in terms of implementation in a template (from 01 = not very complex to implement to 05 = very complex to implement). The criteria are divided also into essential core criteria and advanced criteria that might be desirable for a specific context. The current version of the TF implements all essential core criteria, and some of the advanced criteria.

Figure 9 Quality criteria for DMP templates according to the LOD 5-Star model by Tim Berners Lee²¹

We included all questions of the DFG checklist to ensure that the Science Europe Core Requirements for Data Management Plans (DMPs) are covered. Help texts accompany each question, providing detailed explanations that often include hyperlinks to supplementary resources for further guidance. The questions are also aligned with the research data lifecycle. The framework incorporates questions related to data quality measures and quality control procedures.

The NFDI DMP Template includes predefined answer options for most questions, streamlining responses and promoting consistency. Responsible persons or roles are also requested. Several questions address general legal aspects relevant to research data management including usage rights, copyright law, and ownership issues.

Certain aspects are only partially addressed so far. The FAIR principles are mentioned only briefly within the context of the overall framework, without an in-depth discussion or

²⁰ <https://www.nfdi.de/section-infra/>

²¹ (Krause et al., 2024)

comprehensive elaboration, which may limit their visibility and detailed understanding within specific sections. While the help texts offer some suggestions related to implementing the principles, no specific case studies are included to exemplify the application of FAIR principles in practice.

The template provides a broad, generic framework that encompasses essential content; however, it is designed to be adaptable and must be tailored to the specific needs of individual communities. These specialized aspects are intended to be developed collaboratively with the NFDI consortia, ensuring that the template evolves to address the unique requirements and practices of diverse research communities. However, the extent to which the specific modules should be incorporated into the general framework remains an open question and will require further discussions. Since the TFs goal is to serve as a framework for all consortia, integrating all criteria and too much specific content may not be practical. Further considerations for future developments are described in [Chapter 5](#).

3. Elements of the NFDI DMP Template Framework

The following tables show the structure and questions of the TF and the mapping to the RDA maDMP. The content of the reference catalogs formed the basis for the formulation of the questions. Decisions we made or differences to the RDA maDMP are discussed below each table.

- **Question:** The question addressing a specific topic.
- **Type:** Describes the data type or form that the answers to a question should have, conforming with the RDA maDMP classification of data types.
- **Obligation:** there are two levels. Mandatory fields must be included in the DMP. Optional ones can be included or not. Whether a question is mandatory depends on whether the questions provide a sufficient overview of the respective topic, whether these questions are considered central in discussions with other actors in the RDM field, or whether the questions are required by research funding bodies.
- **Properties:** Mapping to the maDMP standard.
- **Attributes:** Mapping to a corresponding attribute in RDMO.

Notes on understanding the tables:

- Every RDMO attribute uses the prefix <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms> which was excluded for better readability.
- The gray cells indicate that there is no corresponding property in the RDA maDMP for the question so far.
- Yellow cells indicate that these questions are linked by a condition. This means that either a specific option must be activated or the previous question must be answered with 'yes' in order for the subsequent questions to appear in the interview.

The reference catalogs presented in [Step 2](#) formed the basis for the formulation of the questions. Some of them were discussed and adjust with the help of various focus groups.

3.1 Project

Description:

A DMP should contain questions that focus on the overarching circumstances, be it the research project, campaigns, separate events, or similar, within which the DMP is being developed.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Project Title	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/project/title	project/title
What is the main research question of the project?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/project/description	project/research_question/title
When does the project start?	DateTime	optional	rdadmp:dmp/project/start	project/schedule/project_start
When does the project end?	DateTime	optional	rdadmp:dmp/project/end	project/schedule/project_end

Figure 10 Overview of properties in Project

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The question about the *main research question of the project* is optional.

3.2 Project Contact

Description:

This section contains specific questions about project members and responsible parties. These do not necessarily have to be part of the writing team working on the DMP. So far, the TF contains just one question about the *responsible persons or institutions for the project management*, which is mandatory.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?	String	mandatory		project/coordination/name

Figure 11 Overview of properties in Project Contact. (no official RDA maDMP module)

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The TF follows a different logic than the RDA maDMP, namely that the starting point is the *project* and not the *DMP*. Questions about responsibilities, resources, and costs are therefore assigned to the project level.

3.3 Project Funding

Description:

The attributes for the Funder category were selected based on the reference catalogs. As a result, the attribute `project/funder/name` was assigned to the property `funder_id_identifier`. Since there is no equivalent attribute with the same name, and the relevant information was queried via this attribute, it was chosen for this mapping. If the DMP is used for a funded project, the user must at least provide the *name* and a *reference number* of the funder.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Who is funding the project?	String	mandatory	<code>rdadmp:dmp/project/funding/funder_id/identifier</code>	<code>project/funder/name</code>
Project reference number:	String	mandatory	<code>rdadmp:dmp/project/funding/grant_id/identifier</code>	<code>project/funder/grant_nr</code>

Figure 12 Overview of properties in Project Funding

3.4 DMP

Description:

The DMP module covers both issues related to the DMP as a document, such as the version and legal basis, and issues relating to data management. The questions referring to data management are further subdivided into other entities. The question regarding statutory approval is mandatory in this block, even if the answer does not necessarily have to be “yes.”

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Is a statutory approval / permit needed for the research?	Boolean (yes, no)	mandatory	<code>rdadmp:dmp/ethical_issues_exist</code>	<code>project/legal_aspects/official_approval/statutory_approval/yesno</code>

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
If yes, which permit?	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/ethical_issues_description	project/legal_aspects/official_approval/statutory_approval/title
Date:	DateTime	optional	rdadmp:dmp/created	project/dmp/dmp_date
DMP version:	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/modified	project/dmp/dmp_version

Figure 13 Overview of properties in DMP

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The question regarding statutory approval has another possible answer option – ‘unknown’.
- The question ‘Date’ refers to the date on which the DMP was first created. This entry does not need to be changed during the process, whereas the ‘DMP Version’ refers to future changes and should be overwritten each time.

3.5 DMP Contact

Description:

This block and the available question refer to the first point of contact who makes decisions regarding the handling and implementation of the data management. This person may or may not also be the project coordinator. If project coordination and data management are asked about separately, there should be at least one question about the contact person.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Who is the main contact person for questions related to data management?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/contact/name	project/data_management/name

Figure 14 Overview of properties in DMP Contact

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The property ‘name’ is used frequently and, on its own, provides barely information about the context. In the TF, this is specified in more detail using the URI path and a meaningful attribute that includes ‘data_management’ in the title.

3.6 DMP Contributor

Description:

Here all persons and responsibilities that play a role during and after the project can be listed and specified. The following questions provide insight into the areas in which responsible persons should be appointed or which should be given careful consideration during the course of the project in order to keep the data as FAIR as possible. At least, it should be asked whether other subtasks are handled by someone other than the person responsible for data management. Which subareas and subtasks are then asked about depends on the previous answer and the type of project. In this case, there are various options for the question 'Are there other project partners who are responsible for subtasks in the project?', and when one of the options is clicked, one of the following questions appears.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Are there other project partners who are responsible for subtasks in the project?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1A)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/contributor/role	project/partner/name
if one of the options is activated				
Who is also responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?	String	optional		project/support
Who is responsible for the data documentation and for checking the metadata and data documentation for accuracy and completeness?	String	optional		project/dataset/metadata/responsible_person/name
Who is responsible for the backups?	String	optional		project/dataset/data_security/backup_responsible/name
Who is responsible for the maintenance of the PIDs - i.e. the long-term object accessibility?	String	optional		project/dataset/pids/responsible_person/name

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
What Persons or institutions can be mentioned as the long-term contact who can decide on the data?	String	optional		project/dataset/preservation/responsible_person/name

Figure 15 Overview of properties in DMP Contributor

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- There is just one 'role' property, but in RDMO, there are several attributes relating to that information. Therefore, the attribute in the hierarchy above was taken for the first conditional question.

3.7 DMP Cost

Description:

Various costs may arise in a project, which can be specified here, whether for equipment, personnel, or implementation strategies. Since this part is not relevant to all projects, there are no mandatory questions so far.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Which resources (costs; time or other) are required to implement adequate handling of research data within the project?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 P)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/cost/description (rdadmp:dmp/cost/description_costs_non-personnel)	project/costs/usage/non_personnel
What personnel costs are incurred for data management as part of the collection, creation or acquisition of data in the project?	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/cost/description (rdadmp:dmp/cost/description_costs_personnel)	project/costs/creation/personnel

Figure 16 Overview of properties in DMP Cost

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- In the RDA maDMP, the information about cost is dealt unitarily; instead, in all reference RDMO catalogs, costs are allocated to single expenditure items, e.g.

FAIRification, PID registration, long-term preservation. The choice of the "cumulative" vs "fine grained" description depends somehow on the kind of project. Therefore all questions included here are optional.

- There is only one *description* property for the costs, while in the TF there are two questions: one regarding personnel, one regarding non-personnel costs. A specification was therefore added to the respective properties, which are not part of the RDA maDMP.

3.8 Legal Issues

Description:

This entity contains three questions from the DFG checklist that could not yet be mapped to the RDA maDMP. It does not cover the entire scope of the law, but in order to cover all questions from the DFG checklist, these three questions should definitely be included in the DMP. The legal questions that were already included in the RDA maDMP were left unchanged, as this node is solely populated with newly added questions.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues?	String	mandatory		project/legal_aspects/ipr
What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project?	String	mandatory		project/legal_aspects
Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?	String	mandatory		project/additional_rdm_policy/yesno

Figure 17 Overview of properties in Legal Issues. (no official RDA maDMP module)

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- There is no mapping so far, which is why corresponding properties had to be found. Based on the W3C DCAT vocabulary²², which also forms the basis for naming in RDA maDMP, a search was then conducted for corresponding equivalents. As these are

²² <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

very specific questions, the search had to be conducted in linked vocabularies, like the ‘Dublin Core terms’ or the ‘Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)’.

3.9 Dataset

Description:

This module covers all aspects related to the data that are collected or utilized during the research outlined in the DMP. The prerequisite is that the user has first divided their entire data volume into smaller subsets (‘datasets’), for which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc. applies. The following questions therefore need to be answered for each dataset.

In order to get an accurate idea about the dataset, it should not only be treated with questions about its type, which may only be explanatory for the user themselves. Particularly with regard to reuse by others, information should be provided in a way that enables them to know whether this dataset is relevant to their own research without having to look at the data itself. Questions ‘What will this data set be used for and how will it be further processed during the project?’ and ‘What are the reasons for this data set to be retained for the long-term?’ are primarily aimed at this. If reuse is of interest, it is essential to specify when the dataset will be available for use by third parties. The question ‘What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?’ contains several answer options and when the option ‘Using Quality Control Tools’ is activated, it can be specified in more detail within the next question, which has no equivalent in the RDA maDMP so far.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
				project/dataset/id
What kind of dataset is it?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/title	project/dataset/description
What will this data set be used for and how will it be further processed during the project?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/description	project/dataset/usage_description
When is the research data available for use by third parties?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 B)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/issued	project/dataset/data_publication_date
What are the reasons for this data set to be retained for the long-term?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 C)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/preservation_statement	project/preservation/selection_criteria
What measures are being adopted to	Term from controlled list (see	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/data_quality_as	project/dataset/quality_assurance

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
ensure high data quality?	Appendix 1 D)		urance	
if option "Control Tools" is activated				
Which quality controls are in place and how do they operate?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 E)	optional		project/dataset/control_tool
Is existing data reused? If yes, under which address, PID or URL can the dataset be found?	Boolean (yes, no)	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/is_reused	project/dataset/uri
Does this dataset contain personal data?	Term from controlled list (yes, no, unknown)	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/personal_data	project/dataset/sensitive_data/personal_data_yesno/yesno
if "yes"				
What is the retention period for the personal data within the dataset, and how is it justified?	String	optional		project/dataset/sensitive_data/personal_data/deletion
Does this data set contain non-personal sensitive data? If so, which non-personal sensitive data is involved?	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/sensitive_data	project/dataset/sensitive_data/other/description

Figure 18 Overview of properties in Dataset

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- In the RDA maDMP just the first question 'What kind of dataset is it?' is mandatory.
- Even if the attribute 'project/preservation/selection_criteria' for the question 'What are the reasons for this data set to be retained for the long-term?' is not an official dataset attribute, it is used for a question on a dataset level.

3.10 Security and Privacy

Description:

This block is not only concerned with sensitive data, but also with security strategies for all research data within a project. This encompasses not only data containing personal information, but also data that requires protection for other reasons, such as economic interests. The question of data security should be addressed in a Data Management Plan (DMP), regardless of whether it pertains to a single dataset or the entire data collection. A selection of possible security strategies is provided in the available option set.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
What measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g., protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transmission of sensitive data)?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 O)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/security_and_privacy/description	project/dataset/data_security/security_measures

Figure 19 Overview of properties in Security and Privacy

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The information requested here refers only to a specific dataset and is intended to provide information about the handling of sensitive data.

3.11 Technical Resource

Description:

This block refers to the technical systems that are used to generate or process data. In addition, it also addresses what others may require in order to be able to reuse this data.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
What software, processes or technologies are required to use the data?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/technical_resource/name	project/dataset/usage_technology

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Are these data suitable for subsequent use in other contexts? Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 F)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/technical_resource/description	project/dataset/reuse_scenario

Figure 20 Overview of properties in Technical Resource

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- In the RDA maDMP only the name of the technical resource is mandatory.
- The RDA maDMP assumes that these specific devices can be explicitly named and described. However, in the reference catalogs and templates for general RDM, this information would not necessarily be reusable, which is why the questions in the TF were designed to be more open-ended. In certain cases, it may be useful to request precise descriptions of the devices. In this case, it would be useful to adapt and reword the questions, even without changing the attributes

3.12 Metadata

Description:

The metadata block deals with metadata standards that are to be used to describe the dataset. The dataset is not described in detail in this section, but in the *Dataset* block.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
What standards, ontologies, classifications, etc. are used to describe the data and contextual information?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 G)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/metadata/metadata_standard_id/identifier	project/dataset/metadata/standards
Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/metadata/description	project/dataset/metadata/access_info

Figure 21 Overview of properties in Metadata

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- Compared to the RDA maDMP, the TF already provides some suggestions for standards.

3.13 Distribution

Description:

The distribution module covers aspects related to data access and publication of a dataset. Even though the distribution describes the specific form of a dataset, for example a specific file, they might be identical in some cases. The mandatory questions should therefore cover the dataset as comprehensively as possible in order to determine whether the dataset in the host module should be further differentiated.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
			rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/title	dataset/id
Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect new data?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 H)	mandatory		project/dataset/creation_methods
Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be preserved after the end of the project?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 I)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/description	project/dataset/preservation/repository
Which data formats arise in your project?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 J)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/format	project/dataset/format
What is the actual or expected size of the dataset?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/byte_size	project/dataset/size/volume
Will this dataset be published or shared?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 K)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/data_access	project/dataset/sharing/yesno

Figure 22 Overview of properties in Distribution

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The question about the title is the only mandatory question in the RDA maDMP and refers to a unique designation of the distribution, e.g., a specific file name. In the TF, it would be the name for the dataset which a user creates while answering the interview. Additionally, the TF contains a question that is outlined more broadly by looking at how this data was created in order to draw conclusions about the nature of this particular distribution.
- While the expected output type in RDA maDMP is a string for all questions except the last one, the TF provides controlled lists of answer options.
- In the TF, more questions from this area are mandatory in order to know where a fine-grained reference in the host part could be important.
- The question of whether the dataset should be shared or published has three possible answer options in RDA maDMP: *open*, *shared*, and *closed*. In the TF, there are the options *yes* and *no*, whereby the focus here is on specifying who the data should be made accessible to.

3.14 License

Description:

This section can be used to describe in more detail whether there are any restrictions, whether reuse is permitted under a specific license, etc.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Shall the data only be made accessible after an embargo period has expired?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/license/start_date	project/dataset/preservation/embargo_period
Under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 L)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/license/license_ref	project/dataset/sharing/conditions

Figure 23 Overview of properties in License

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- The RDA maDMP requires a specific date from which the data will be accessible. In the TF a string is required, so that it is possible to specify the exact terms of a possible embargo.
- In the RDA maDMP a URL to the used license is required, whereas in the TF possible answer options are provided. Every answer option shall be connected with an URL in the future.

3.15 Host

Description:

In the RDA maDMP, each distribution has just one host. In contrast, in the TF it is also possible to have many hosts within each distribution. The host is the storage location of the distribution, which includes all types of systems that are used within and after the project. A host can therefore be split into multiple locations depending on the distribution. An open issue is that if there are multiple hosts, they must also be described with multiple metadata. There may also be different licensing of the data/metadata, which is not covered so far.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Where is the data deposited and made accessible?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/title	project/dataset/sharing/repository
Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 M)	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/availability	project/dataset/sharing/restrictions_explanation
What system of persistent identifiers shall be used?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 N)	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/pid_system	project/dataset/pids/system
How is the data to be stored throughout the project duration?	Term from controlled list (see Appendix 1 O)	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/storage_type	project/dataset/storage/type
Is a technology or tool used for versioning?	Term from controlled list (yes, no, unknown)	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/support_versioning	project/dataset/versioning_tool
How and how often will the data be backed up?	String	optional	rdadmp:dmp/dataset/distribution/host/backup_frequency	project/dataset/data_security/backups

Figure 24 Overview of properties in Host

Differences to the RDA maDMP:

- Only the question about the title of the location, where the data is stored, is mandatory.
- The properties *availability* and *storage_type* recommend a string, whereas the TF provides several controlled lists for the related questions.

4. The Template Framework in RDMO

For easier reuse of the framework, we developed the RDMO catalog “NFDI DMP Template”. It is intended to support consortia in creating domain-specific DMP templates based on the framework and its standardized attributes. For better use of the interview-style approach in RDMO (see [X.II](#)), we decided to rearrange and regroup some questions of the framework. This makes it easier for users to answer the dataset-related questions in RDMO. The complete RDMO catalog can be found in [Appendix 2](#). It is also available on GitHub²³ and can be reused in an own RDMO instance.

Figure 25 illustrates where the content of the individual modules of the RDA maDMP is taken up in the catalog.

Figure 25 Used mappings in the RDMO “NFDI DMP Template”

Since the “data management” and “DMP” section play a superordinate role in the RDA maDMP and form the starting point for all further nodes, they are dealt with at the beginning of the first section in the NFDI DMP Template. Not all properties could be mapped, as data management has only played a minor role in the catalogs examined. In contrast, the project plays a key role, as it is the starting point for inquiries about funding, resources, and contact persons.

²³ https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/shared/DMP4NFDI/2025-06-26_dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0.xml

All questions in the “Legal Issues” node in the adapted maDMP model are taken from the DFG checklist and were split into two groups: questions relating to the current project and questions relating to the time beyond the end of the project.

The second major area in the RDA maDMP is focused on the term "dataset", which refers to the entire data pool as a logical subdivision. There is some leeway regarding the interpretation of what a dataset is, which is after all decided by the data producers. Some criteria and recommendations are currently being developed in the RDMO sub-working group *UAG editorial processes* and are based on the following criteria:

- origin/generation: generated (observation/measurement, experiment, survey, simulation, web-crawl...) or reused;
- storage (space) requirements: e.g.: <1GB, ~10TB;
- documentation requirements: e.g. extensive description of survey sampling and survey implementation; reference to metadata to re-used data retrieved from a research data repository;
- data privacy aspects: personal data, sensitive non-personal, public data;
- relevance/reuse potential: high (reference data), middle (scientific main study), low (preliminary study).

In the RDMO domain, the number of attributes relating to datasets are equally weighted. 142 of 307 attributes relate to datasets²⁴. As shown in Figure 25, the entire area relating to the description of data is divided into sub-groups in order to establish a logical structure for the sequence of the questions. While there are only a few categories in RDA maDMP that contain a large number of properties, the NFDI DMP Template aims to examine the individual topics in greater detail.

In our workshop at the e-Science-Tage conference in Heidelberg in 2025, one of the topics discussed was that the distinction between “host” and “distribution” is not sufficiently differentiated (Schönau et al., 2025). In the RDA maDMP, each dataset can have multiple distributions, each of which is assigned to only one host. A distribution “is used to mean a particular instance of a dataset that has been, or is intended to be, made available in some fashion”²⁵ and “host” describes the technical solution in which the distribution is stored or can be found. In the TF, there can be multiple hosts for each distribution, depending on the question. The NFDI DMP Template Catalog represents this. Figure 25 shows that the entity host plays a role in many areas of the RDMO catalog, but the questions only address one dataset. For example, data may not be publicly available, but the associated metadata may be. Currently, such a scenario can be represented in the NFDI DMP Template only by creating different datasets. In the future, different answers per distribution will be possible by providing answer options in the related conditional question.

It is possible that detailed treatment of some topics is only relevant in certain disciplines, while a general query is sufficient for others. During the DMP4NFDI integration phase, discipline-specific adjustments and enhancements to the TF will therefore be aspired with the help of the consortia. However, the NFDI DMP Template Catalog can already be reused in RDMO and adapted to specific requirements.

²⁴ Status 06/2025

²⁵ <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard?tab=readme-ov-file#distribution>

4.1. Benefits of using the RDMO DMP Template

The RDMO DMP Template can be utilized in various ways. While individual templates are being developed for the NFDI consortia, the TF serves as a consensus-driven foundation for DMP topics relevant to all consortia. It is built on standardized attributes aligned with the international standard for machine-actionable DMP templates established by the Research Data Alliance (Miksa et al., Version 1.1). This ensures that the information collected is interoperable and can be seamlessly exchanged between systems as a starting point for creating machine-readable DMPs. Plugins developed for one consortium can more easily be reused by others. The TF's flexibility allows for selective reuse of questions or sections, and it can also serve as a source of inspiration for creating custom questions using relevant attributes. The following subsection illustrates a scenario where the TF is used to create a new template from scratch.

4.2 Workflow to (re)use the RDMO DMP Template

The RDMO Editor's Guide on *how to develop a catalog in RDMO*²⁶ explains in detail how RDMO catalogs are created and elements are hierarchically structured (see Figure 26). Nevertheless, we provide some recommendations on how to implement and adjust the catalog in RDMO.

All elements in RDMO are structured hierarchically. In particular, attributes are connected to parent attributes and the full path indicates their logical placement. Other elements such as questions, pages, and sections are also arranged hierarchically. When developing a catalog, this hierarchy must be taken into account to keep track of the order in which individual elements are created. The top-level element is the *catalog* element. The next level comprises the various sections of a catalog, which each in turn contain pages, questions, and question sets. A page cannot be created in a catalog unless a section has been created as the intermediate element.

Figure 26 Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

²⁶ <https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/management/catalog-development.html>

Step 1: Importing the NFDI DMP Template and changing the RDMO prefix

In order to reuse the NFDI DMP template and adapt it to your own needs, it is recommended to make a full copy of the catalog/section/page/question first, renaming all prefixes.

- The Prefix should indicate the context in which the template was created, whether this is through institutional affiliation or assignment to a specific subject area. When creating consortium-specific templates, a standardized prefix for the respective consortium should be considered.
- Even if the URI is a non-resolvable link, it should comply with the following format which is a de-facto standard in the RDMO community:
 - [https://\[your-namespace\]/terms](https://[your-namespace]/terms), e.g. <https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms>

Step 2: Adding new content

The following suggestions are only recommendations for a structured approach. However, if you wish to integrate new content into the TF, these suggestions should be implemented following the described procedure.

Adding new questions:

- The URI of a questions is composed of:
 - the URI Prefix: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms>
 - the “questions/”
 - and the URI path, which corresponds to the classification in the TF, e.g. DMP/Project/rdadmp_title for the question about the project title.
- In the TF, the corresponding RDA maDMP field to the question is mentioned in the URI path.
- If there is already a property that matches the supplemented question but no corresponding attribute, DMP4NFDI or the RDMO community can help to find the right one or to create a new attribute and, if appropriate, integrate it into the RDMO domain.

Adding new options:

- The prefix of new options should always be the same as of the parent option set, and we recommend to use the following system for the keys of the options
 - Options of the option set [prefix]options/contributor_responsibilities should be named ‘[prefix]cr00’, ‘[prefix]cr01’, ‘[prefix]cr02’ and so on.

- The NFDI DMP Template reuses option sets from other catalogs, so this naming convention is not always the case.
- If a new option set is being created, use the same URI prefix as the one used for the entire catalog.

Adding new modules:

- If larger blocks are to be integrated into the catalog, it is advisable to create a separate area for them, either in separate sections or on separate pages. This can simplify reuse.
- The URI prefix should be used consistently. The URI path can correspond to the area in the RDA maDMP. It is also possible to connect all topics contained in the path of the section with an underscore and to use only parts of the name in the lower pages, see Figure 27.

Figure 27 A passage from the NFDI DMP Template catalog in RDMO

- If the new blocks refer to a specific question of the NFDI DMP template, it might make sense to move this question to the newly created section and supplement it with further questions. It is also possible to link the question of the NFDI DMP template to a condition, so it remains in its original place and the other questions appear when specific options are selected.

5. Future Developments

The framework is now available in its first version and can be utilized to create domain-specific, but interoperable DMP templates. We expect a need to continuously improve the framework until we reach a broad consensus across all NFDI consortia. Several consortia have already committed to build templates based on the framework in cooperation with DMP4NFDI. Adding domain-specific modules will further enhance the framework and prove its usability.

Further versions of the framework will incorporate the forthcoming update of the RDA maDMP standard. This influences both the mapping of attributes to properties and the NFDI DMP template in RDMO, because there are already some necessary thematic extensions. DMP4NFDI is currently involved in the update of the RDA maDMP which is expected to be published in 2025. Our work and findings on necessary areas of a DMP are also fed back into the RDA *DMP Common Standards WG*²⁷.

So far, we have already identified several possible adjustments:

- In order to map the many-to-many relationship between distribution and host in a more granular way, the topics of reuse, sharing, and archiving in particular need to be coordinated better.
- In addition, the topic of digital preservation is still underrepresented, and there are ideas to develop a separate node that can be integrated into the framework.
- To turn the TF into a maDMP, additional plugins with connections to other systems (e.g., PID systems for metadata import or validation), will be developed. This also prevents having strings as value types, which complicates using the DMP as a maDMP.
- For maximizing the benefits for researchers, we plan to improve the explanations of the FAIR principles throughout the framework. Also, the TF should account for all project phases so it can be more effectively applied before, during, and after the project.
- For the second funding phase of the basic service, DMP4NFDI also places a stronger emphasis on software management plans
- There are some RDMO attributes whose names do not seem to really fit the content of the questions, but are incorporated for interoperability reasons (e.g. `project/data_management/name` or `project/additional_rdm_policy/yesno`). We will exchange with the RDMO community on renaming those attributes.

Building on our modular Train-the-Trainer (TtT) concept for DMPs and RDMO (Gonzalez Ocanto et al., 2025), we will support and train NFDI consortia staff responsible for DMP development. The TtT concept offers a multi-tiered training structure with three levels: fundamentals, advanced, and expert. Training on the TF will be included on the second level (advanced) of the RDMO module, equipping participants with the skills needed to create interoperable and standardized catalogs using the TF.

²⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg/activity/>

6. Acknowledgements

This publication, as part of the DMP4NFDI service, was made possible by Base4NFDI. Base4NFDI is funded by DFG, as part of NFDI, under project number 521453681.

There are also many parties who have contributed to developing the NFDI Template Framework in its current form. We thank all participants of our workshops, who provided feedback to our work. We express our sincere thanks to the NFDI LTA working group for the productive collaboration, valuable input, and the helpful text modules provided. We are also grateful to PID4NFDI for their suggestions and contributions, and to Neelam Bhanupratap Vishen for her valuable input on data protection and legal aspects.

7. References

- Castro, L. J., Diederichs, K., Gonzalez-Ocanto, M., Jagusch, G., Johannsen, J., Lindstädt, B., Rebholz-Schuhmann, D., Schmitz, D., Schönau, S., Stäcker, T., Windeck, J., & Wallace, D. (2025). DMP4NFDI - NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans. Proposal Integration Phase (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15482168>
- Diederichs, K., Krause, C., Lemaire, M., Reidelbach, M., & Windeck, J. (2024). A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570654>
- Enke, H., Hausen, D., Henzen, C., Jagusch, G., Krause, C., Schönau, S., Weimer, L., & Windeck, J. (2023). Data management planning: Concept for Setting up a Working Group in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructures (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7540682>
- Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771036>
- Hastik, C., Windeck, J., & Schönau, S. (2023). FDM4Ing Community Meeting CC-42: Introduction in RDM and using RDMO for your engineering projects. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10262633>
- Hausen, D. A., & Andres, A.-C. (2024). Chemistry-specific Data Management Plan Template based on DFG checklist. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948510>
- Klar, J., Michaelis, O., Wallace, D., Schröder, M., Fütterer, H., Malzer, C., Lanza, G., Martínez Muñoz, D., Piloni, D., & Enke, H. Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) [Computer software]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.596581>
- Krause, C., Bergmann, K., Hausen, D. A., Riedel, R., & Windeck, J. (2024). Quality Criteria for DMP Templates (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13347687>
- Markus, K., Naumann, K., Schmalzl, M., Watson, J., & Triebel, D. (2024). Langzeitarchivierung in der NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822613>
- Markus, K., Leinen, P., & Stäcker, T. (2025). Concept for Setting up an LTA Working Group in the NFDI Section "Common Infrastructures". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14939132>
- Miksa, T., Walk, P., & Neish, P. RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans (Version 1.1) [Computer software]. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>
- Miksa, T., Walk, P., & Neish, P. (2020). RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>
- Schönau, S., Diederichs, K., Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). Workshop Report: Developing the NFDI DMP Template Framework (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15605949>
- Science Europe. (2021). Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

8. Appendix

Appendix 1: Optionsets of the Template Framework

- A. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/contributor_responsibilities
- B. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_availability
- C. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/preservation_motivation_options
- D. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_quality
- E. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/control_tools_long
- F. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_reuse_context
- G. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_description_standards
- H. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_new_data
- I. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/preservation_repository_options
- J. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/file_formats
- K. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dataset_sharing_options
- L. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dataset_license_types
- M. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_publication_restrictions
- N. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/pid_system
- O. Optionset https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_storage
- P. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/resources_non-personnel
- Q. Optionset https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/security_measures

Appendix 1 A: Optionset contributor_responsibilities

Question	Are there other project partners who are responsible for subtasks in the project?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/contributor_responsibilities
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:role
Option Text	Additional Input
There are further contact persons for data management.	no
There are further contact persons for data curation.	no
There are further contact persons for the field of metadata.	no
There are further contact persons for the topic of backups.	no
There are further contact persons for the field of data preservation.	no
Other	yes

Figure 28 Optionset contributor_responsibilities

Appendix 1 B: Optionset dataset_availability

Question	When is the research data available for use by third parties?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_availability
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:issued
Option Text	Additional Input
In all probability already during the project	yes
Immediately after the end of the project	yes
1 year after the end of the project	yes
2 years after the end of the project	yes
5 years after the end of the project	yes
10 years after the end of the project	yes
Subsequent years after the end of the project	yes
The data record will not be usable for third parties.	no
This data set is reused by us and already published	yes

Figure 29 Optionset dataset_availability

Appendix 1 C: Optionset preservation_motivation_options

Question	What are the reasons for this data set to be retained for the long-term?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/preservation_motivation_options
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:preservation_statement
Option Text	Additional Input
Basis of a publication / proof of good scientific practice	no
Re-use in subsequent projects or by others	no
Legal obligations	no
Documentation, because of their societal relevance	no
Self-commitment	no
Other	yes

Figure 30 Optionset preservation_motivation_options

Appendix 1 D: Optionset dataset_quality

Question	What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_quality
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:data_quality_assurance
Option Text	Additional Input
Using a calibration method	yes
Repetitions of measurements	yes
Validation of data input and data output	yes
Use of a predefined quality criteria catalogue	yes
Use of a controlled vocabulary	yes
Verification by experts	yes
Training/awareness coaching for project staff	yes
Using Quality Control Tools	no
Other	yes

Figure 31 Optionset dataset_quality

Appendix 1 E: Optionset control_tools_long

Question	Which quality controls are in place and how do they operate?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/control_tools_long
RDA maDMP Property	not yet defined
Option Text	Additional Input
Data collection - instrument calibration (accuracy/scale)	no
Data collection - multiple measurements, observations or samples	no
Data collection - verification by experts	no
Data collection - using standardised methods and protocols (with clear instructions)	no
Data collection - computer-assisted data collection (standardised, Verified, consistency)	no
Digitization and data entry - validation rules or input masks	no
Digitization and data entry - Controlled vocabularies, code lists, and pick lists to minimize manual data entry.	no
Digitization and data entry - Detailed labeling of variable and record names	no
Digitization and data entry - using a purpose-built database structure to organise data /data files	no
Digitization and data entry - Accompanying notes and documentation about the data	no
Data verification - double check of data and outlier values	no
Data verification - checking completeness	no
Data verification - Verifying random samples against the original data	no
Data verification - Check for double entry of data	no
Data verification - Statistical analyses such as frequencies, means, ranges or clustering to detect errors and anomalous values	no
Data verification - Correcting errors made during transcription	no

Figure 32 Optionset control_tools_long

Appendix 1 F: Optionset dfg_reuse_context

Question	Are these data suitable for subsequent use in other contexts? Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_reuse_context
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:description
Option Text	Additional Input
Yes, the data can be used scientifically by	yes
Yes, re-using the data in teaching is conceivable.	no
Yes, my research is socially relevant and the data can be reused by society.	no
Yes, because	yes
No, I can't imagine a future use scenario for the data, because	yes

Figure 33 Optionset dfg_reuse_context

Appendix 1 G: Optionset dfg_description_standards

Question	What standards, ontologies, classifications, etc. are used to describe the data and contextual information?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_description_standards
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:metadata_standard_id/identifier
Option Text	Additional Input
Discipline-specific standards, classifications, etc. are used	yes
A proprietary description system is used, which looks like this	yes
The description system used is documented in more detail at the following address	yes
The repository we work with uses the standard:	yes
Other	yes
As part of the project, it is determined which system is to be used to describe the metadata and context information.	no
No specific scheme is used.	no

Figure 34 Optionset dfg_description_standards

Appendix 1 H: Optionset dfg_new_data

Question	Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect new data?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_new_data
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:title
Option Text	Additional Input
Observations (by humans, instruments or sensors)	no
Polls	no
Surveys	no
Laboratory experiments	no
Social science experiments	no
Field experiments	no
Analysis, derivation or compilation from other data sources	no
Calculations	no
Bibliographies	no
Catalogues, repositories or databases	no
Crowdsourcing	no
Web scraping	no
Models	no
Simulations	no
Other	yes

Figure 35 Optionset dfg_new_data

Appendix 1 I: Optionset preservation_repository_options

Question	Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be preserved after the end of the project?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/preservation_repository_options
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:description
Option Text	Additional Input
Own institution	no
Another partner institution	yes
Discipline specific data centre	yes
Generic data centre	yes
To be decided	no
Other	yes

Figure 36 Optionset preservation_repository_options

Appendix 1 J: Optionset file_formats

Question	Which data formats arise in your project?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/file_formats
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:format
Option Text	Additional Input
Application	yes
Audio	yes
Image	yes
Message	yes
Model	yes
Text	yes
Video	yes

Figure 37 Optionset file_formats

Appendix 1 K: Optionset dataset_sharing_options

Question	Will this data set be published or shared?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dataset_sharing_options
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:data_access
Option Text	Additional Input
Yes, externally for everyone	no
Yes, externally limited with individual approval	no
Yes, internally with everyone, as long as they don't pass on the data	no
No	no

Figure 38 Optionset dataset_sharing_options

Appendix 1 L: Optionset dataset_license_types

Question	Under which terms of use or license will the data set be published or shared?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dataset_license_types
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:license_ref
Option Text	Additional Input
Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)	no
Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC-BY-NC)	no
Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives (CC-BY-ND)	no
Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC-BY-SA)	no
Open Data Commons Attribution	no
Open Data Commons Open Database	no
Public domain (CC0)	no
Other, or exact designation – if known	yes

Figure 39 Optionset dataset_license_types

Appendix 1 M: Optionset dfg_publication-restrictions

Question	Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_publication-restrictions
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:availability
Option Text	Additional Input
Yes, the data are subject to a non-disclosure agreement. A publication can be made in	yes
Yes, we work with personal data.	no
Yes, publishing the data would violate the intellectual property rights of third parties.	no
Yes, the data cannot be published due to the following legal aspects	yes
No, there are no restrictions.	no

Figure 40 Optionset dfg_publication-restrictions

Appendix 1 N: Optionset pid_system

Question	What system of persistent identifiers shall be used?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/pid_system
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:pid_system
Option Text	Additional Input
ark	no
arxiv	no
bibcode	no
doi	no
ean13	no
eissn	no
handle (e.g. ePIC)	no
igsn	no
isbn	no
issn	no
istc	no
lissn	no
lsid	no
pmid	no
purl	no
upc	no
url	no
urn	no
other	yes

Figure 41 Optionset pid_system

Appendix 1 O: Optionset dfg_storage

Question	How is the data to be stored throughout the project duration?
Related Optionset	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_storage
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:storage_type
Option Text	Additional Input
Facility's central storage and data management service	yes
Central cloud service of the facility	yes
GitHub/GitLab	no
Other cloud solution	yes
Central solution (e.g. network disks and automatic data mirroring, use of the institution's central server infrastructure, archiving of data on university servers, etc.)	no
Decentralized solution (e.g. server in the institute or chair, etc.)	no
Local computer	no
external hard drives	no
other	yes

Figure 42 Optionset dfg_storage

Appendix 1 P: Optionset resources_non-personnel

Question	Which resources (costs; time or other) are required to implement adequate handling of research data within the project?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/resources_non-personnel
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:description_costs_non-personnel
Option Text	Additional Input
infrastructure resource: archives	yes
infrastructure resource: data base	yes
infrastructure resource: server	yes
infrastructure resource: licenses for software	yes
The following additional infrastructure resources are required	yes
Personnel expenses by the institute	yes
Personnel expenses in the project	yes
Other	yes

Figure 43 Optionset resources_non-personnel

Appendix 1 Q: Optionset security_measures

Question	What measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g., protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transmission of sensitive data)?
Related Optionset	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/security_measures
RDA maDMP Property	rdadmp:description
Option Text	Additional Input
Access Control Lists (ACLs)	yes
Data Encryption	yes
Data Recovery	yes
Anonymization / Pseudonymization	yes
Data Loss Prevention (DLP) Tools	yes
Regular Security Audits and Penetration Testing	yes
Incident Response Plan	yes
Other	yes

Figure 44 Optionset security_measures

Appendix 2: The NFDI DMP Template in RDMO

Appendix 2 provides the structure, questions and help texts of the NFDI DMP Template in RDMO.

Catalog NFDI DMP Template

Section General Information

Page General Project Information

Question: Project Title:

Help: Please provide the full title of the project.

Question: What is the main research question of the project?

Help: Please briefly describe the project and its objectives.

Question: When does the project start?

Help: Enter the expected date if the project has not yet started.

Question: When does the project end?

Help: Enter the expected date if the project has not yet started.

Question: Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

Page Project Funding

Question: Who is funding the project?

Question: Project reference number:

Page General DMP Information

Question: Date:

Help: Today's date

Question: DMP version:

Help: Which version of the data management plan is this?

Question: Is a statutory approval / permit needed for the research?

Value type: Boolean (yes / no)

Question: If yes, which permit?

Page Legal Restrictions regarding the Research Project and DMP

Question: What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project?

Help: Examples include: does the legal situation in different countries have to be taken into account? Does every employee have the same access rights? Is there personal data, possibly even with special protection requirements? Are there contractual regulations for data transfer, for example in the case of industrial data? Are there third parties who have (copyright) rights to the data? Is the data subject to export control regulations? Take into account that long-term access and reuse including migration to current file formats, transfer of data between systems and between responsible organisations needs rights for copying (in context of copyright), clearly defined access rights and reuse rights which must be applicable far into the future.

Question: Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?

Help: Name specific requirements here that are relevant to your discipline and your scientific work. In addition to general scientific codes, there can also be specialist codes. If you do not know these, you can find out more from the NFDI consortium that has emerged in your discipline. The [DFG's page on scientific integrity](#) also provides information. Here you will find references to laws, subject-specific comments on the guidelines and explanations, case studies and [further links to legal and ethical frameworks](#).

Page Responsibilities and Resources

Question: Who is the main contact person for questions related to data management?

Help: This question refers to tasks that arise during the project phase. Assignments of responsibilities beyond the project phase can be specified in the question "What Persons or institutions can be mentioned as the long-term contact who can decide on the data?".

We recommend specifying the person in the following form: title; first name, last Name; ORCID (if available); professional position; affiliation; contact details; role in the project.

Question: Are there other project partners who are responsible for subtasks in the project?

Optionset: contributor_responsibilities – see [Appendix 1 A](#)

Question: Who is also responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?

Question: Who is responsible for the data documentation and for checking the metadata and data documentation for accuracy and completeness?

Question: Who is responsible for the backups?

Question: Who is responsible for the maintenance of the PIDs - i.e. the long-term object accessibility?

Question: What Persons or institutions can be mentioned as the long-term contact who can decide on the data?

Question: What personnel costs are incurred for data management as part of the collection, creation or acquisition of data in the project?

Help: Please estimate the effort in person-months (1 PM = monthly working time of a full-time employee).

Question: Which resources (costs; time or other) are required to implement adequate handling of research data within the project?

Help: Name both the resources that you bring in as your own contribution or as part of the basic equipment, as well as the resources for which you are applying for funds.

This can involve technical or IT resources as well as expertise that is brought in, for example, by data managers or IT experts.

If necessary, provide more detailed information on the respective items.

Optionset: resources_non-personnel — see [Appendix 1 P](#)

Section Data Description

Page Content Data Description

Question: What kind of data set is it?

Help: The following questions serve to describe the data sets that are created and/or used in the project. The definition of what a data set is, is an important conceptual decision that must be made individually for each undertaking or project. Choose a logical unit of your research data as the data set, for which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc. applies.

The division into data sets helps to assess the value of the data with regard to potential subsequent use, publication and digital preservation or long-term storage. Since all questions have to be answered for each individual data set, an overly fine-grained structure does not make sense.

The [DFG defines research data](#) very broadly. Based on this definition, research data is processed in every project. So try to identify and describe your data products in the research process. You are also welcome to refer to other places in the application if, for example, the data or methods are described in more detail there.

Question: Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect new data?

Help: This information is necessary to be able to reconstruct the process by which the data was generated. It is also a prerequisite to judge the objectivity, reliability and validity of the data set.

For reproducible data it is also required to re-generate the data if necessary. Therefore all devices, software, software version and also information about the procedure necessary to be able to re-create the data must be preserved.

Optionset: dfg_new_data — see [Appendix 1 H](#)

Question: Is existing data reused? If yes, under which address, PID or URL can the data set be found?

Help: This includes data from previous projects that may only have been shared internally upon request, as well as publicly or commercially available data. Should, for example, a comparison with old measurements be part of the project or if an old data set is to be evaluated under new aspects, this can be indicated here. Ideally, you provide a citable source (e.g. via a DOI) for the data. Alternatively, you can indicate the project or context in which the data was created if data from other scientists was reused. Otherwise, it is advisable to indicate that no suitable data is available based on your own research.

Explanation:

Some data can in principle be recreated at any time. Examples of this are scientific experiment data or digital copies of analog objects (as long as the originals are not lost). The effort and costs for this can of course be quite considerable. With regard to the question of the need for digital preservation at a later date, the effort involved in creating a new document should be weighed against the effort involved in digital preservation. Other data, on the other hand, cannot be collected again per se. This is the case, for example, with any kind of episodic observation, be it social science or natural science, as these depict a specific phenomenon at a specific point in time and/or place and are therefore usually not repeatable. Their value for subsequent use by others as well as unsuccessful or skipped publication of data in a trusted data repository or transfer to a digital archive for digital preservation is incomparably higher than that of reproducible data.

Value Type: Boolean (Yes, The URL is / No)

Page Technical Data Description

Question: Which data formats arise in your project?

Help: When choosing a data format, one should consider the consequences for collaborative use, digital preservation and long-term storage as well as re-use. It is advisable to prefer formats that are standardized, open, non-proprietary and well-established in the respective scholarly community. Recommendations can be found in [How to FAIR](#), for example.

The options to be selected are based on the media types suggested by the RDA from <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>. Select an option and specify the corresponding format, e.g. in the form text/csv.

Optionset: file_formats — see [Appendix 1 J](#)

Question: What will this data set be used for and how will it be further processed during the project?

Question: What is the actual or expected size of the dataset?

Help: Please enter the approximate quantity as a number with the corresponding unit of measurement.

If large amounts of data are involved, financial resources for the provision of the infrastructure should be considered (see also page "Responsibilities and Resources").

Section Documentation and Data Quality

Page Data Documentation

Question: What standards, ontologies, classifications, etc. are used to describe the data and contextual information?

Optionset: dfg_description_standards — see [Appendix 1 G](#)

Question: Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Help: This is important if access to the data is subject to restrictions but not excluded, e.g. is subject to conditions or requires special software.

Question: What software, processes or technologies are required to use the data?

Help: In order to be able to reuse data, in addition to the data itself, the software, if applicable (measuring) devices etc. and knowledge of special procedures for use are required.

Since usage can vary depending on the discipline, either discuss with your colleagues or contact the [NFDI consortium](#) for your discipline if you don't know exactly what is needed.

As for data formats: the more standardized, open and established methods and tools are, the easier it is usually to reuse data.

The establishment of standards for methods, use of software, collection of research data and description of research results is an essential prerequisite for the comparability and transferability of research results.

Page Data Quality

Question: What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?

Help: Depending on the discipline, the quality of the data can be ensured by various measures.

Optionset: dataset_quality – see [Appendix 1 D](#)

Question: Which quality controls are in place and how do they operate?

Help: Quality controls can relate to both the processes and the data itself. If necessary, describe which automated controls or controls by other persons are planned.

Optionset: control_tools_long – see [Appendix 1 E](#)

Section Storage during the Project

Page Data Storage

Question: How is the data to be stored throughout the project duration?

Help: Storage is relevant for data actively in use as well as finalized data. Please note that depending on the storage location, your data is not automatically backed up. You can find out advantages and disadvantages of storage media at www.forschungsdaten.info.

The DFG expects here a description of the infrastructure you use for data storage and backup. In particular, describe the use of storage and backup infrastructure offered centrally at your institution or justify your use of local or (subject)-specific solutions.

Optionset: dfg_storage – see [Appendix 1 O](#)

Question: Is a technology or tool used for versioning?

Value Type: Term from controlled list (yes, no, unknown)

Question: What system of persistent identifiers shall be used?

Help: If, after completing the project phase, you decide to use an external data repository that uses DOIs as persistent identifiers (PIDs), it makes sense to take the DOI metadata requirements into account during the project phase. This will avoid having to make adjustments to the metadata later on and reduce the additional effort involved in preparing your research data for publication and archiving.

Optionset: pid_system – see [Appendix 1 N](#)

Page Backup

Question: How and how often will the data be backed up?

Help: This question refers to backups while the data is being worked with. Long-term storage issues are addressed in the appropriate section.

Question: What measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g., protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transmission of sensitive data)?

Help: Sensitive data can appear in various contexts, such as personal data, economic cooperation projects, geolocation data, or licensed data.

- For personal data and its security, contact your institution's local data protection officer.
- For economic cooperation projects, refer to non-disclosure agreements for access and usage rights.
- Usage conditions for licensed data are detailed in the license agreements.

Select all applicable answers and describe the implementation to ensure unauthorized access, prevent data loss and make data recovery possible:

- For protection against unauthorized access, emphasize the importance of granular access control mechanisms like ACLs to restrict access to data based on roles and permissions.
- For data encryption, describe, what procedures ensure protection of the data at rest and in transit, ensuring unauthorized users cannot access the information?
- For data recovery backups or multiple replicas in a distributed file system would be valuable possibilities. Here you should describe the strategies to ensure data recovery in case of an incident. Data Loss Prevention (DLP) tools can help to prevent accidental or malicious data exfiltration.
- If personal or sensitive data is processed, how do you employ robust anonymization techniques to make data unidentifiable, or pseudonymization to make re-identification harder but possible? How often are security audits and penetration tests conducted to identify and address vulnerabilities?
- Does the organization have an incident response plan in place to handle data breaches, and what measures ensure its effectiveness?

Optionset: security_measures — see [Appendix 1 Q](#)

Section Data Exchange and long-term Data Accessibility

Page Reuse

Question: Are these data suitable for subsequent use in other contexts? Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset?

Help: Please consider whether your data can be reused. The reusability of data does not mean its publication, but e.g. the value of the data for follow-up projects, new

collaborations, etc. In the evaluation, it can also play a role whether data can be generated again.

This is the case for digital versions of analogue objects (if the originals are still available), generally but often with great effort also for experiments in natural sciences. Such data do not necessarily have to be preserved. On the other hand, any time-related data - time series, episodic events such as earthquakes, also social science surveys - are not repeatable unique observations.

Optionset: dfg_reuse_context – see [Appendix 1 F](#)

Question: What are the reasons for this data set to be retained for the long-term?

Help: “Retained” includes publishing, sharing, long-term storage and/or digital preservation of data.

Optionset: preservation_motivation_options – see [Appendix 1 C](#)

Question: When is the research data available for use by third parties?

Help: According to the [DFG Guidelines for Research Data Management](#), research data should be made available as soon as possible and ideally according to the [FAIR principles](#).

The importance of data publication is underscored once again by the [Guideline 13 of the Code of Good Scientific Practice](#). Discipline-specific practices are pointed out here.

Select the appropriate option and, if possible, specify the exact date in the form YYYY-MM-DD.

Optionset: dataset_availability – see [Appendix 1 B](#)

Page Sharing

Question: Will this dataset be published or shared?

Help: It is advisable to ensure open access to research data generated in projects according to the principle of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”. This means that data is generally open unless you decide, for legitimate reasons, to restrict access to some or all of your research data. Metadata is generally openly accessible. This definition of sharing includes offering data to an archival institution with respective legal mandates (e. g. a national archive, a state archive).

Optionset: dataset_sharing_options – see [Appendix 1 K](#)

Question: Where is the data deposited and made accessible?

Help: Please provide information about the repository/database. In order to allow digital preservation of your data, deposit it in a trustworthy data repository (TDR).

Question: Under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?

Help: Refer to the Creative Commons Licenses. Use the text field to specify licenses, including details like CC BY 4.0 International. For code refer to software licenses (<https://choosealicense.com/>). If not provided by the publication or sharing service, add machine readable URLs in the metadata, e.g. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> or <https://spdx.org/licenses/MIT.html>, so that the legal situation regarding the handling of the data is permanently secured and accessible. If use of general licenses is not possible, specify access rights (which group of persons or which personnel function is allowed to access data under which conditions?) and which usage rights apply (is copying and reuse in general or for research allowed. Be aware that every transfer to another system and many maintenance and preservation actions are inherently copying data).

Optionset: dataset_license_types – see [Appendix 1 L](#)

Question: Does this data set contain personal data?

Help: If yes, ensure that the Data Usage and Data Storage and Security sections include measures that comply with applicable data protection laws, such as:

- GDPR (EU): General Data Protection Regulation
- Germany: Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG)
- State-specific laws (e.g., DSG NRW for North Rhine-Westphalia)

The GDPR defines personal data as information related to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art. 4 GDPR, para. 1). A person is:

- Identified: Clearly recognizable as the data subject.
- Identifiable: Can be identified using additional information.

If your data falls in the personal data category, it is a good practice to consider the following instruments in place:

- Data Processing Agreement (DPA): If the research involves the processing of personal data in a joint research project, inquire about the existence of a DPA between the collaborating institutions.
- Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA): Include a question about whether a DPIA has been conducted, as required by the GDPR for high-risk data processing activities.
- Data Subject Rights: Remind researchers of their obligations to ensure data subjects are aware of their rights (e.g., access, rectification, erasure).

Value Type: Term from controlled list (yes, no, unknown)

Question: What is the retention period for the personal data within the dataset, and how is it justified?

Question: Does this data set contain non-personal sensitive data? If so, which non-personal sensitive data is involved?

Page Archiving and Digital Preservation

Digital preservation (also called long-term preservation) facilitates accessibility, authenticity and reusability of data over a long time span, especially beyond changes of technology, hardware, software and standards. In contrast to storage during the project, the timespan is not defined in years, it is understood as an indefinite time period during which technological and organizational changes will take place. It is typically carried out by a responsible and trustworthy preservation service. Digital preservation aims for long-term access and reuse, including measures such as migration to current file formats, transfer of data between systems and between responsible organisations and usually follows best practices like CoreTrustSeal certification or nestor certification.

Please select data for preservation, clarify where it should be preserved and specify which personnel transfers the data need to be ready for a preservation service/ data service/legal archive or similar. Take into account that a preservation service/archive may have its own sets of guidelines and regulations. The transfer may be conducted after a specified period during which data are simply stored. A publication service may also already include preservation or may transfer data to a preservation service/digital archive or similar automatically.

Question: Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be preserved after the end of the project?

Help: Data should be deposited with a service that at least provides backup and monitors integrity of the bitstream, with clear responsibility who maintains the backup and integrity functions. The service should also allow findability based on the metadata deposited alongside data (data themselves do not have to be openly accessible).

Optionset: preservation_repository_options — see [Appendix 1 I](#)

Question: Shall the data only be made accessible after an embargo period has expired?

Help: If yes, provide a clear justification for the embargo period and explain the rationale and expected benefits. Inquire about the mechanisms for monitoring and reviewing the embargo period to ensure its continued necessity.

Section Legal obligations and conditions

Page Publication Restrictions

Question: Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?

Help: It is possible that there are reasons that can speak against a (direct) publication of the data. This can be, for example, the protection of personal data or the commercial or industrial use of the data. Confidentiality related to security issues can also be a reason. You can find more information in [Guideline 13 of the code on Good Scientific Practice](#).

Please keep in mind that the data can be published after a certain blocking or embargo period and that you can also prepare this publication now.

Optionset: dfg_publication-restrictions – see [Appendix 1 M](#)

Question: What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues?

Help: Aspects of use and copyright as well as questions of ownership must be taken into account on the one hand when you use data from others and on the other hand when you generate data. If you generate your own data, you should clarify which rights are relevant. If you generate data together with partners, you regulate who has what rights of disposal to the data. For later use, you should explain which legal rules apply and, if applicable, under which licenses you will make the data available (publication and sharing, long-term storage and/or digital preservation).

Various rights can play a role in data. Whether your data is subject to copyright protection depends, among other things, on the level of originality. Information on this can be found, for example, in the [information sheet on copyright protection of research data \(only available in German\)](#), or [Research Data Copyright and Licensing \(only available in German\)](#).